

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SMART IRRIGATION USING IOT

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Abstract

Water scarcity and inefficient irrigation practices pose significant challenges to agriculture, leading to decreased crop yields and environmental degradation. In response to these challenges, this study presents the design and implementation of a Smart Irrigation System (SIS) utilizing Internet of Things (IoT) technology. The proposed system aims to optimize water usage, enhance crop productivity, and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

Smart irrigation systems leverage IoT devices such as sensors, actuators, and controllers to monitor and manage various parameters related to soil moisture, weather conditions. These devices collect data from the field and transmit it wirelessly to a central control unit or mobile phone. The key components of a smart irrigation system include soil moisture sensors, temperature sensors and solenoid valve. These components work in tandem to optimize water usage by providing precise irrigation scheduling based on actual plant needs and environmental factors. Furthermore, smart irrigation systems enable remote monitoring and control, allowing farmers to access real-time data and adjust irrigation settings from anywhere using a smartphone or computer.

Keywords: Smart farming, Data analytics, IOT (Internet of Things), sensors networks, Remote Monitoring, Precision agriculture.

1. Introduction

Drip irrigation is a method of watering plants by applying small, precise amounts of water directly to the roots of the plants, typically through a network of tubing, emitters, and valves. This irrigation technique is highly efficient and economical, as it minimizes water wastage by delivering water exactly where it's needed, reducing evaporation and runoff. Drip irrigation systems require lower pressure compared to other irrigation methods, resulting in energy savings, especially when using pumps. Drip irrigation can be used in various landscapes, including gardens, orchards, vineyards, and agricultural fields, catering to different plant types and soil conditions. Overall, drip irrigation offers a sustainable and effective solution for efficient water management in agriculture, landscaping, and gardening, promoting healthier plant growth while conserving water resources. Drip irrigation systems integrated with Internet of Things (IoT) technology offer numerous benefits by enabling remote monitoring, control, and optimization of irrigation processes. IoT sensors can be installed throughout the drip irrigation system to monitor key parameters such as soil moisture levels, temperature, humidity, and weather conditions. These sensors continuously collect data and transmit it to a central control system or cloud platform in real-time. By continuously monitoring soil moisture levels and weather conditions, IoT-enabled drip irrigation systems can optimize water usage by delivering the right amount of water at the right time. This minimizes water wastage, reduces runoff and leaching, and promotes sustainable water management practices. Overall, the integration of IoT technology with drip irrigation systems offers a powerful tool for enhancing water management, increasing crop productivity, and promoting sustainable agriculture practices.

Fig no.1 (drip irrigation system)

Fig no.2 (IOT based dripping system)

2. Literature

The most significant contributor to recent breakthroughs in technical development is machine learning. In light of current advancements in the process control business, it is prudent to consider the expectations of both the client and the server when making crop recommendations through the Internet, trustworthy magazine articles, and machine learning algorithms of choice. It is broken down using the many resources that are readily accessible, such as the conferences that support the system. Web journals that may be accessed online provide useful information and, in most cases, offer advice and remedies in the event of a problem. It is necessary to be able to foresee such issues and deceptions, which may lead to catastrophic repercussions if they are not overcome. Technologies that use artificial intelligence (AI) have been able to forecast the behavior of nonlinear systems and have contributed to managing variables in order to enhance the operational conditions of the system. A new study highlighted the rise of artificial intelligence as a potential aspect of the answers for increased agricultural production.

Alejandro Pannunzio et.al Irrigation systems should be a relevant agent to give solutions to the increasing demand of food, and to the development, sustainability and productivity of the agricultural sector. The design, managing, and operation of irrigation systems are crucial factors to achieve an efficient use of the water resources and the success in the production of crops and orchards. The aim of this paper is to analyse knowledge and investigations that enable to identify the principal criteria and processes that allow improving the design and managing of the irrigation systems, based on the basic concept that they facilitate to develop agriculture more efficient and sustainable. The design and managing of irrigation systems must have its base in criteria that are relevant, which implies to consider agronomic, soil, hydraulic, economic, energetic, and environmental factors. The optimal design and managing of irrigation systems at farm level is a factor of the first importance for a rational use of water, economic development of the agriculture and its environmental sustainability.

Abdelraouf Ramadan Eid et.al As for population of more than 90 million, peoples cannot meet its need for food as adequate water is not available for crop production. So to identify and adopt measures that will reduce water use and increase crop production, this study was conducted in farmers' fields during 2009/2010–2010/2011 to evaluate the water use efficiency and economic viability of sprinkler irrigation system for growing wheat crop. Two field experiments were conducted in the Research and Production Station of the National Research Centre in El-Nubaria El-Behera Governorate. The water-use characteristics of wheat were studied in the field under sprinkler irrigation system.

Rajni Jain et.al In India, spatial and temporal variation of precipitation has been boundless varying from 11000 mm to 90 mm. The average annual per capita water availability has declined from 5000

cubic meter in year 1950 to 1545 cubic meter in year 2011 and estimated to reduce further to 1341 and 1140 cubic meter in year 2025 and 2050, respectively. Agriculture sector, which provide 54.6% of total employment to growing population, alone consumes more than 90% of total groundwater draft in irrigation. Over the years, groundwater has become dominant source of irrigation due to its independent access and timely availability of water.

Karthikeyan et.al Drip irrigation is one of the water saving technology which is used for the potential usage of the available water. The traditional form of irrigation is surface irrigation, where water will flow in the land to reach the destination of the crops, this will lead to wastage of water. But, Drip irrigation is a technology which will take the water directly to the root of the crops through the pipes. This technology will increase the productivity of the crops. The findings is about the factors that drives the adoption of drip irrigation in Erode district in Tamil Nadu, India. Despite many advantages in the drip irrigation many farmers in the district have not adopted to the drip irrigation, so the findings also analyses the reasons for the farmers to not adopt drip irrigation, including financial constraints, water scarcity, no subsidy from the government, damages by the animals, high maintenance cost, lack in technical skills, etc.

Imran Arshad Management of the drip irrigation system requires proper knowledge of the system, climate and suitable environmental conditions for the cultivated crops. To achieve good management practices for drip irrigation, the impacts of climate variables on plant growth and production during different seasons should be understood. The planning of irrigation system and installation of components in the right way is considered one of the most essential matters to ensure the highest efficiency possible use of available irrigation water and allows the plants to benefit from the most water used. Assessment of the irrigation system and improving its efficiency involves many variables, the details concerning the parts of the irrigation system and also the method of its management and maintenance. The maintenance includes repair and replaces any of the parts of the irrigation system to prevent leaks and closures. Also, it includes maintenance and washing the filter and irrigation pipes to remove the accumulated impurities and salts.

Bhagya Jayant et.al Irrigation can be defined as the process of applying artificial water to soil or land in order to promote the growth of agricultural crops such as corn and wheat. Water irrigation has a number of advantages, including an increase in crop yield, protection against famine, revenue generation, and the avoidance of mixed cropping. It also has advantages in navigation, hydroelectric power generation, and the creation of employment opportunities. It should be noted that irrigation has both advantages and disadvantages, just like everything else. Irrigation has a number of disadvantages, including the waste of irrigation water, the formation of marshy lands, damp weather, and the loss of valuable agricultural land. Drip irrigation is one of the surface and subsurface irrigation methods that we will discuss in this paper. We will also discuss the various effects and advancements in this technique that have occurred as a result of the research conducted. Last but not least, the significance and necessity of this system will be discussed.

Ameer Hussain Jarwar et.al the drip irrigation is a type of micro irrigation system that as the potential to save the water and other nutrient by entering in water to drip gradually drip to water entrance

by nutrients other and water the salvage to potential buried or surface soil the on from is which ,parts plant other and plants of roots main the into directly water place to is irrigation drip of aim main the .vapor water the decrease and zone root main depending Its .valves and ,pipes ,emitters ,tubes different of shape schematic a through drip system a ,is it operated and ,installed ,maintained ,make it well how designed the on as like ,systems irrigation drip of types various other than useful more be can irrigation introduced firstly is irrigation drip system The .irrigation surface or irrigation sprinkler it ,ever More society the to benefits economic and social other various presents also the under or soil of surface the on ,drop by drop by or jet micro utilized is water system research deeply ,research this our In .soil the of infiltration the than rate lower a at ,soil advantages upcoming its and irrigation drip system for management. Crops and to identify the constraints encountered by farmers in adopting the drip irrigation for horticultural crops. The results revealed that majority of drip irrigation farmers had expressed.

Prof T Chandrasekhar et.al In the field of agriculture, use of proper method of irrigation is important and it is well known that irrigation by drip is very economical and efficient. In the conventional drip irrigation system, the farmer has to keep watch on irrigation timetable, which is different for different crops. The project makes the irrigation automated. With the use of low cost sensors and the simple circuitry makes this project a low cost product, which can be bought even by a poor farmer. This project is best suited for places where water is scares and has to be used in limited quantity. Also, third world countries can afford this simple and low cost solution for irrigation and obtain good yield on Crops. A 16×2 LCD is connected to the microcontroller, which displays the humidity level and ambient temperature. The humidity sensors are constructed using aluminium sheets and housed in easily available materials. The aim is to use the readily available material to construct low-cost sensors. Five relays are controlled by the microcontroller through the high current driver IC, ULN2003.

2.1 SUMMARY OF LITERATURE SURVEY

- Uneven distribution of water. Some crops get more water while some crops get less water.
- Waterlogging is another issue in uneven land.
- It requires the use of cattle and human labor; thus, it is less efficient.

2.2 OBJECTIVES

- To Develop and install of automate drip irrigation system for vegetables.
- To work out the cost economics of the automatic drip irrigation system.
- To develop user friendly mobile based application to control developed automatic irrigation system Using IOT.

2.3 METHODOLOGY

2.4 WORKING PRINCIPLE

Soil moisture sensors are embedded in the soil at various locations within the field or garden. These sensors measure the moisture content of the soil. The moisture sensor data is collected and transmitted to a central control unit using wireless communication protocols such as Wi-Fi. The central control unit receives the data from the soil moisture sensors and processes it to determine the irrigation requirements. Based on predefined requirement, the control unit decides whether irrigation is needed or not. If the soil moisture level falls below a certain threshold, indicating the need for water, The control unit sends signals to actuators, such as solenoid valves, to open or close the water flow to the drip irrigation system. When the control unit determines that irrigation is necessary, it activates the drip irrigation system, allowing water to flow through the drip emitters.

and deliver water directly to the plant roots. The system continues to monitor soil moisture levels and adjusts the irrigation schedule dynamically based on real-time data. This feedback loop ensures efficient water usage and optimal plant growth.

2.5 COMPONENTS USED

- Arduino UNO and ESP8266 are two popular microcontrollers used in DIY electronics and IoT projects. The Arduino UNO is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P chip. One of the main advantages of using the ESP8266 with an Arduino UNO is that it allows the Arduino to connect to a Wi-Fi network and communicate over the internet. This makes it possible to create IoT projects that can be controlled and monitored remotely. The Arduino UNO board has 14 digital input/output pins, 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz quartz crystal, a USB connection, a power jack, and an ICSP header for programming the board with an external programmer. The board also has a built-in LED connected to pin 13, which can be used for testing and debugging.

Model: ESP8266-12E

Wireless Standard: 802.11 b/g/n

Operating temperature: from -40°C to +125°C

Dimensions (mm): 58×31.20×13

Weight: 10 grams

- A Relay is a simple electromechanical switch. While we use normal switches to close or open a circuit manually, a Relay is also a switch that connects or disconnects two circuits. But instead of a manual

operation, a relay uses an electrical signal to control an electromagnet, which in turn connects or disconnects another circuit.

- Soil moisture sensors measure the volumetric water content in soil. Since the direct gravimetric measurement of free soil moisture requires removing, drying, and weighing of a sample, soil moisture sensors measure the volumetric water content indirectly by using some other property of the soil, such as electrical resistance, dielectric constant, or interaction with neutrons, as a proxy for the moisture content.
- The LM2596 is a type of voltage regulator, specifically a step-down (buck) converter. It is an integrated circuit that provides the necessary functions for converting a higher input voltage to a lower output voltage. The LM2596 is commonly used in various electronic devices and power supply applications.
- A water pump is used to move, compress, or transfer water from a lower level to a higher one. The main purpose of a water pump is to transfer water between two points and to get rid of excess water.

Head=20mm

Hp=0.5

Reduced Head=40mm

Operating Power =240v

Rate Of Speed=2880Rpm

Discharge=850lph

- solenoid valves operate on electricity to automatically start and stop flow. The actuator is directly mounted to the valve body to minimize movement and reduce wear Solenoid valves are electrically operated devices used to control flow. They are used for the remote on/off or directional control of liquids, gases and steam.

Normally closed type: Water flow starts when power is ON, and closes when power is OFF.

Copper winding solenoid valve

Pressure: 0.2 - 8 bar

Power: 230 Volts AC, 200mA

Material: Plastic

Outlet: ½ inch

Inlet: ½ inch

- In lateral farming, irrigation is done by the help of gravity. water is supplied to the topmost row and adequate amount is allowed to fall to the bottom rows. this prevents wastage of water and largely prevent surface evaporation and seeping of excess water.

- An arrow dripper is a dripper used in drip irrigation to irrigate crops. The arrow dripper is also called a stake dripper. The arrow dripper has a drop leading stake which is used to irrigate crops on farms, greenhouses, grow bags and pots. The arrow dripper is the most appropriate type of dripper for plants grown in pots and grows bags. The arrow dripper is flexible as it can be used almost anywhere. It sticks into the soil or substrate and supply water to the plant therein.
- A hose connector is a device used to join or attach two sections of a hose together or to connect a hose to a different component, such as a faucet, sprinkler, nozzle, or another hose. These connectors are essential in various applications where fluid, usually air or water, needs to be transferred efficiently and effectively.

2.6 Calculation:

Lateral calculation

Data Collected.

- $M=0.2\text{ltr/sec}$
- Lateral Dia= 0.012m
- $\rho=1000\text{kg/m}^3$

Area of lateral pipe

$$A=(\pi \cdot D^2)/4$$

$$(\pi \cdot (0.012^2))/4$$

$$\mathbf{A = 0.0012\text{m}^2}$$

Velocity of water flow

$$M=\rho \cdot A \cdot V$$

$$0.20=1000 \cdot 0.0012 \cdot V$$

$$\mathbf{V=0.178\text{m/sec}}$$

Dripping Calculation

Data Collected.

- 70sec for 100ml
- 182 grow bags

$$=3600/70$$

$$\mathbf{=51.42}$$

$$=51.42 \cdot 100$$

$$\mathbf{=5.142\text{ltr/hr}}$$

Water consumed per bag

$$=5.142/4$$

$$\mathbf{=1.285\text{ltr/15min}}$$

Water consumed for overall bag

$$=1.285 \cdot 180$$

$$\mathbf{=233.99\text{ltr/15min}}$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL WORK:

Arrow dripper discharge

SL.NO	Water in (ml)	Time in(min)
1	250	2.45
2	500	5.30
3	750	8.15
4	1000	11
5	1250	13.45

A measurable beaker has taken, and water is discharged from lateral pipe. In the beaker the water is measured for 500ML in 2.5 seconds and for the various water discharge rate from lateral pipe is tabulated above.

Lateral discharge

SL.NO	Water in (ml)	Time in(sec)
1	250	147
2	500	318
3	750	489
4	1000	660
5	1250	805

A measurable beaker has taken, and water is discharged from arrow dripper. In the beaker the water is measured for 500ML in 147 seconds and for the various water discharge rate from arrow dripper is tabulated above.

Soil Moisture Sensor Reading

SL.NO	Moisture level (PH)	Water pump status
1	10%	ON
2	20%	ON
3	30%	ON
4	40%	ON
5	50%	OFF
6	60%	OFF
7	70%	OFF

8	80%	OFF
9	90%	OFF
10	100%	OFF

Soil moisture level is measured, and it turns ON the pump when preset threshold values are sensed that are tabulated above.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Comparison

Fig 8.1.2 Manually watering the grow bags

Fig 8.1.3 Watering the grow bags with IOT dripping system

Approximate water consumed per grow bag
 =2.5ltrs
 =2.5*182
 =455ltrs

approx. labor cost
 =300*365
 =109500 /yr.

water consumed per grow bag.
 =1.285ltrs
 =1.285*182
 =233.99ltrs

Fig 8.1.3

In this method it takes approximately 45 mins for watering overall grow bags

Fig 8.1.4

In this method it takes exactly 15 mins for watering overall grow bags

By shifting from manually watering method to IOT dripping system. We saved **221ltrs** of water and **30mins** of time.

4.2 GRAPHS

Lateral discharge

Time v/s Quantity of water Discharge in Lateral Pipe

The discharge from the lateral pipe is the same across the various quantity of water. For 500 ml of water it takes 2.5 seconds.

Arrow dripper discharge

Time v/s Quantity of water Discharge in Arrow dripper

The discharge from the Arrow dripper is same across the various quantity of water. For 500 ml of water it takes 318 seconds.

Water Discharge in Both the Methods

Time V/S Quantity of Water

In this graph the time taken by both manually watering, and drip irrigation values are being compared to each other.

Water Consumed in Both the Methods

Quantity of Water v/s Type of Watering Method

In this graph the Water Consumed by both manually watering, and drip irrigation values are being compared to each other.

Labor Cost in Both the Methods

Cost v/s Type of Watering Method

By Comparing both Manual and IOT Drip Irrigation the cost reduction is graphically shown above.

In Manual Watering the labor cost is ₹109500

In IOT Drip Irrigation the initial and
The maintenance cost is ₹25000.

Per day labor cost is ₹300

Initial Cost is ₹18500

For 365 Days

Maintenance and Electricity Cost is ₹6500

$$300 \times 365 = ₹109500$$

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

5.1 Conclusion

1. The design and implementation of smart irrigation using IoT offers a promising solution for efficient water management in agriculture.
2. By integrating sensors, actuators, and data analytics, this system optimizes irrigation schedules based on real-time environmental conditions, soil moisture levels, and plant requirements.
3. By precisely measuring soil moisture levels, the system can deliver water only when and where it's needed, minimizing water waste and total liters of water saved in IOT based dripping system for **182 growbags** is **221 litres** and water usage is reduced by **49%**.
4. Farmers can remotely monitor soil moisture levels and adjust irrigation schedules using their smartphones saving time and effort here labor cost is saved by Rupees **84500/yr**. By Implementing IOT Drip Irrigation System the labor cost is reduced by **77%**.
5. Plants receive the right amount of water at the right time, leading to healthier growth and higher yields of the crop. By reducing water usage and optimizing irrigation, farmers can lower their water bills and potentially increase profits

5.2 Future Scope:

- Installing solar panels for electrical supply.
- Addition of temperature sensor.
- Addition of fertilizer sensor to detect the fertilizer percentage and requirement of fertilizer.

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